

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE NEED FOR THE PRINCIPLE OF "LIFELONG LEARNING" IN PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ ПРИНЦИПА "ОБУЧЕНИЕ НА ПРОТЯЖЕНИИ ВСЕЙ ЖИЗНИ" В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ

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Abstract

The article highlights the question of the principle of lifelong learning during professional development. The article also provides analytical information about the current situation in Uzbekistan. Organization, together with the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, of the process of professional development of public education workers on the principle of "lifelong learning", the introduction into practice of the procedure for professional development in accordance with an individual development program developed on the basis of the diagnosis of professional needs of employees, the phased introduction of a continuous professional development system into the process of professional development of industry workers on the basis of credit-modular issues are listed.

Аннотация

В статье освещен вопрос о принципе обучения на протяжении всей жизни при повышении квалификации. В статье также представлена аналитическая информация о сегодняшней ситуации в Узбекистане. Организация совместно с Министерством высшего и среднего специального образования процесса повышения квалификации работников народного образования по принципу "обучение на протяжении всей жизни", внедрение в практику порядка повышения квалификации в соответствии с индивидуальной программой развития, разработанной на основе диагностики профессиональных потребностей работников, поэтапное внедрение в процесс повышения квалификации работников отрасли системы непрерывного профессионального развития на основе кредитно-модульного перечислены вопросы.

Keywords: educational sphere, planned, public education, teaching staff, information, experimental and testing, professional development system.

Ключевые слова: образовательная сфера, плановое, государственное образование, педагогические кадры, информационные, опытно-испытательные, система повышения квалификации.

Successful implementation of reforms requires a certain amount of time and opportunity. In particular, reforms in the field of education are a complex process that requires consistency, a thorough and thoughtful plan, analysis and research. By this time, however, there was no special organization or institution in the public education system that would research the problems of the industry, define its strategy and scientifically study and test the planned innovations [1].

The decree of the president "on measures for the development of education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan", adopted on November 6, 2020, as well as the decision "on additional measures to further improve the education system", defined specific tasks for further improvement and scientific support of reforms in the public education system.

In these documents, special attention was paid to issues related to the retraining and professional development of public education employees, and the task was set to transform the leaders and pedagogical workers in the field into a continuous system of professional

development based on the principle of "reading throughout life" [2].

According to the current regulation, pedagogical personnel should be trained at least 1 time every 5 years, and leader and specialist personnel-at least 1 time every 3 years. The fact that the teacher is trained in 5 years for 1 month, that is, on the basis of a 144-hour training program, and the remaining 4 years and 11 months are not involved in any studies, leads to the fact that they do not work on themselves, do not enjoy a large amount of educational information.

The professional development of pedagogical personnel 1 time in 5 years has now been preserved only in some CIS countries. Education in the world in developed countries, continuous professional development of teachers is established every year [3]. For example, in the Republic of Korea, the teacher is prescribed at least 108 hours of training annually, in Singapore and Japan more than 100 hours annually, in the Netherlands-166 hours.

Therefore, it has become an urgent issue for us to train employees of the industry not periodically, but constantly, to organize professional development based on the professional needs of employees. This, in turn, places even more responsibility on the part of the Institute: establishing a competitive and effective national education system, improving textbooks and teaching aids based on the requirements of the time, optimizing educational programs and standards, researching and finding solutions to scientific problems related to the professional development of heads and pedagogical workers of educational institutions-the main activity of the Ministry of public education, together with the state inspectorate for quality control of Education and the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education, was tasked by June 1, 2021 to organize the process of professional development of public education employees on the principle of "reading throughout life", to introduce into practice the procedure for professional development in accordance with the "To what extent did the content of the course you studied meet your professional needs, which was recently given to employees who studied at the advanced training course? 20 percent of them "fully satisfied", 20 percent "partially satisfied", 50 percent "did not satisfy", and 10 percent responded "I do not know". Many of those involved in the survey noted that if their needs were taken into account in the formation of advanced training programs, the benefit and effect of the course would have increased [4].

In order for any educational process to be effective, it must correspond to the interests and needs of the person receiving the education. It is characteristic of Educators of all ages and is especially important for older people. A pedagogue-employee goes to a professional development course, usually in order to receive innovations, master new methods and technologies of teaching, meet his professional needs. However, the professional need varies in each educator. This is natural. The topic that will be transferred to 25 pedagogical staff concentrated in one audience may be interesting for someone, correspond to someone's needs, and not give anything to the rest at all. Ultimately, the mentioned course or advanced training course will not be able to satisfy the audience at the same level. To do this, it is necessary to study the needs of public education employees for professional development, draw up an individual trajectory of professional development for each of them, and organize training on this basis [5].

To implement a needs-based professional development system, differentiated training programs are developed based on the level of qualification, knowledge, scientific and pedagogical potential of public education employees, work experience and the trajectory of individual professional development. In addition to traditional advanced training, harmonized, combined with the work process, distance and other alternative forms of vocational training are introduced, and information on individual trajectories of public education employees, the results of professional development and mastered training programs are entered into their electronic portfolio.

A credit-module system is introduced in advanced training. Assessment of the results of professional development education based on the needs of pedagogical and personnel requires a new approach [6]. According to the current regulation, the listener, after completing the advanced training course, goes through a final assessment process, which consists in testing and protecting the qualification work. These forms of assessment are used for advanced training courses organized on the basis of a unified curriculum and training programs. However, the results achieved by listeners who studied on the basis of various individual trajectories and curriculum programs cannot be assessed by a single assessment tool-the protection of test and qualification work.

When assessing the results of education in the system of continuous professional development of public education employees, the introduction of a credit-modular system is being determined [7]. According to him, the minimum size of loans (academic hours) is envisaged, which should be collected by the employee in a year. Each employee, having mastered the training modules provided to him through the above-mentioned platform "Continuing Professional Education", is evaluated by the platform, and the accumulated credits are concentrated in the employee's personal account. An employee who has fallen a fixed amount of loans is considered to have completed a refresher course for this year.

The introduction of the credit-modular system of assessment makes it possible to evaluate the results that employees also receive in alternative forms of advanced training. It is also established to assess in loans such cases as the employee's use of electronic resources on the internet, such as Coursera, raising his level, preparing students for Republican and international Olympiads, publishing articles in prestigious scientific journals abroad, defending a dissertation for a degree. A healthy competitive environment is created. It is determined to involve higher educational institutions and non-governmental educational organizations in the field of pedagogy in the processes of professional development of public education employees, and ultimately create a healthy competitive environment [8].

To date, the qualification of employees of public educational institutions has been carried out in the regional centers of retraining and professional development of 14 employees of public education in the Institute and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent.

In the structure of higher educational institutions, it is established to establish the fakultets of professional development of public education employees, to establish the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami as a base educational institution for higher educational institutions authorized to improve the qualifications of public education employees, to develop model educational plan, program, educational-methodical and other documents of the courses of It is also envisaged to take measures to constantly update the educational and methodological support of courses, to develop scientific and methodological and organiza-

tional and methodological foundations for the introduction of effective forms of advanced training [9]. The tasks of developing the skills of modern methods of organizing the educational process in pedagogical workers, developing the skills of mastering advanced pedagogical, information and communication and innovative technologies and their active application to the educational process using the internet world Information Network, multi-media systems and distance learning methods in public education employees are envisaged.

Now public education employees will be able to improve their skills not only in professional development organizations under the Ministry of public education, but also in any state and non-state educational institutions located in the regions at their discretion.

This procedure will end the existing monopoly on advanced training, create a healthy competitive environment in the field of advanced training by providing the opportunity to choose. Regardless of where the employee is trained, it is required to collect credit scores established for the current year [10].

The public education system has acquired its own scientific research institute. Our institute is entrusted with the tasks of scientific and methodological support of field activities, conducting fundamental, practical and innovative research, introducing their results into practice and implementing research programs and projects on the actual problems of general secondary education.

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